

Review Article

Structure of the Universe II

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Introduction

For some reason, Astronomers are perplexed that the so-called Hubble Constant varies between 68 and 73 for an average value of $141/2=705$

The Universe is NOT expanding; it is being compressed as anyone who has read my papers should know. My papers have been available in book form for almost 20 years and in Journals for almost 8 years.

Here are some calculations for you to think about.

There are holes in the Ether. The ether is Teflon or Carbon Tetrafluoride. The Superforce is $8/3$ and follows the sine waves. It is cyclical.

In Astrotheology, the Force is equal to $\sin t$

$$y=y'$$

$$v-a$$

$$\sin 45 \text{ degrees} = \cos 45 \text{ degrees} = 1/\sqrt{2} = (68+73)/2 = 707.$$

$$V = Hod$$

$$(1/\sqrt{2})(4/3) = 948809$$

$$948809 - 5.1099 e^- = 938.7 \sim \text{Mass of a proton} = 938.27 \text{ MeV}$$

$$v = d/t$$

$$t = d/v = (4/3)/(1/\sqrt{2}) = 942.8 = M p +$$

$$M = \ln t = \ln [(4/3)/(1/\sqrt{2})] = 346$$

$$\text{But } t = -KE = 1/2 M v^2$$

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$$= 1/2(346)(948.809)^2$$

$$= 1/2 (346)c^2$$

$$= 15.574$$

$$1 - 0.15574 = 0.84431 = \sin 1$$

$$\ln (1/5000) = 0.8517 = 1/117.4 = \text{Mass of the Periodic Table}$$

The universe is being compressed by the Superforce. The Red Shift is solely the result of an expanding universe. The Superforce compresses the light causing a shift.

$$F = Ma = 8/3 = M(1/\sqrt{2})$$

$$M = 377 = 1/265 \sim 1/F = E = 1/\sin t = 1/0.866 = 1.1547$$

$$M = \ln t$$

$$t = e^M = e^{115.47}$$

$$= 317 = 1/\pi = \text{Frequency of the Superforce}$$

$$t = 1/\text{freq}$$

$$1/\text{freq} = 1/G$$

$$G = \text{freq}$$

$$1 - t =$$

$$1 - \pi = 2.14159265$$

$$2.14159265 \times 7 = 6.670 = G$$

$$M = 1/81 = 0.012345679$$

There are 7 cycles of time.

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